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Formulation of *Hygrophila auriculata* (Neeramulliya)-based herbal tea with anti-urolithiatic activity (prevention of kidney stone formation)

S.R.G.R. Madushan^{1*}, H.R.G. Jayawardhana¹, T.C. Kananke¹, R.M.K.T. Rathnayaka¹,
R.M.U.S.K. Rathnayaka¹, M.N. Wickramaratne², G.P.L. Supulchandra³,
and M.G.A.N. Perera¹

¹Department of Physical Sciences and Technology, Faculty of Applied Sciences,
Sabaragamuwa University of Sri Lanka, Sri Lanka.

²Department of Biochemistry, Faculty of Medicine, Sabaragamuwa University of Sri Lanka.

³Food and Nature (Pvt) Ltd, No 106/6A, Araliya Uyana, Depanama, Pannipitiya, Sri Lanka.

Urolithiasis, commonly known as calculi or stones in the urinary tract, is a result of calcification in the kidneys, ureters, bladder, or urethra. Patients with urolithiasis experience severe pain and are generally managed with alpha-receptor blocker medication or surgical removal of the stones. Many studies have revealed that Ayurvedic medicine and herbal remedies offer a potential alternative for the prevention and control of urolithiasis by preventing calcium oxalate crystallization and precipitation. The present study aimed to develop an herbal tea formulation based on *Hygrophila auriculata* (HA), known as Neeramulliya, and to determine the effect on the inhibition of urolithiasis *in vitro*. Tea formulations were prepared by blending black tea (*Camellia sinensis*) with dried HA leaves in four different ratios. The anti-urolithiasis activity of each combination of tea extract was evaluated by measuring the crystallization kinetics of calcium oxalate using turbidity at 620 nm at 37 °C, compared to the crystallization rate in the absence of tea mixture. Trisodium citrate was used as the positive control. Our results exhibited inhibition of calcium oxalate crystallization at all combinations of (black tea: HA) mixtures. The black tea: HA in 3:1 ratio exhibited the maximum inhibition (96%), while the lowest activity was shown at black tea: HA in 1:3 ratio with an inhibition percentage of 90%. Both pure black tea and HA extracts showed 60% inhibition of crystal aggregation. Black tea and HA show greater activity when those two are present as a blend than individually. Our findings revealed the potential of *Hygrophila auriculata* and black tea mixture to be used in the development of novel herbal tea blends as a preventive and management approach for urolithiasis. This study demonstrates an interdisciplinary approach, bridging traditional herbal medicine with modern scientific techniques, to develop innovative solutions for public health issues. Further investigations using animal trials and clinical trials are essential to confirm its efficacy and safety in humans.

Keywords: Herbal tea, *Hygrophila auriculata*, kidney stones, prevention, Urolithiasis

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E-mail: srgmadushan@gmail.com